

Global GPM-IMERG feature-associated precipitation identifiers

Wei-Ming Tsai¹, Suqin Duan¹, Travis O'Brien², Jennifer L. Catto³, Paul Ullrich⁴, Yang Zhou⁵, L. Ruby Leung⁶, Zhe Feng⁶, Willam Boos⁷, D. L. Suhas⁷, Fiaz Ahmed¹, J. David Neelin¹

University of California, Los Angeles¹; Indiana University Bloomington²; University of Exeter³; University of California, Davis⁴; Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory⁵; Pacific Northwest National Laboratory⁶; University of California, Berkeley⁷

Abstract

The data collection provides 0.25-deg., 6-hourly global feature-precipitation categories from 2001 to 2019. The data is generated by merging GPM-IMERG observational rainfall (V6 final version) and atmospheric features identified by multiple object-based algorithms. Classified precipitation identifiers include rainfall associated with atmospheric rivers (AR), frontal systems (FT), low-pressure systems (LPS), mesoscale convective systems (MCS), and their co-occurrences (overlapping areas of features at a given time). In addition to algorithm-identified features, precipitation contributed from deep convection, non-deep convection, stratiform, and drizzle are pixel-wise defined using thresholds of CPC MERGE-IR brightness temperature and GPM-IMERG rain rate. The dataset is supported by the Department of Energy and Environment (DOEE): DE-SC0023244.

Data description

1. Data structure

Name	GPM-IMERG feature-precipitation identifiers
Period	January 2001 to December 2019
Spatial and temporal resolutions	0.25 degree on the ERA-5 latitude-longitude coordinate (0-360°, 60S-60N), 6-hourly
Data format	NetCDF (version 4.9.1)
Variable	<p>Precipitation identifier [<i>precip_id</i>] (time, latitude, longitude): An integer number (1-20) that indicates a specific precipitation source</p> <p>Single feature: (1) AR (2) Front (3) MCS (4) LPS Two-feature: (5) AR-Front (6) AR-MCS (7) AR-LPS (8) Front-MCS (9) Front-LPS (10) MCS-LPS Three-feature: (11) AR-Front-MCS (12) AR-Front-LPS (13) AR-MCS-LPS (14) Front-MCS-LPS (15) All (16) Unexplained: missing values of observational rainfall or brightness temperature</p> <p>[post-defined with MERGE-IR brightness temperature and GPM-IMERG] (17) Deep convection (18) Non-deep convection (19) Stratiform (20) Drizzle</p>

Parameters	CC-threshold (cold cloud): 250 K linearly decreasing to 230 K from 30-deg to 60-deg. Deep convection ($T_b \leq \text{CC-threshold}$, $P > 0.5 \text{ mm/hr}$); None-deep convection ($T_b > \text{CC-threshold}$, $P > 0.5 \text{ mm/hr}$); Stratiform ($T_b < \text{CC-threshold}$, $P < 0.5 \text{ mm/hr}$); Drizzle ($P > 0.5 \text{ mm/hr}$)
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2. Method

Identification of feature-associated precipitation

The categorization of global precipitation relies on recognizing four primary atmospheric features: atmospheric rivers (ARs), fronts (FTs), mesoscale convective systems (MCSs), and low-pressure systems (LPSs). Initially, identified atmospheric features with varying temporal and spatial resolutions are harmonized into a unified framework (6-hourly and 0.25-degree). GPM-IMERG precipitation data (0.1-degree resolution) is then coarse-grained to 0.25-degree for labeling using merged feature outputs. Additionally, precipitation attributed to deep convection, non-deep convection, stratiform, and drizzle is discerned at the pixel level using MERGE-IR brightness temperature data alongside GPM-IMERG precipitation. These classifications exclusively apply to rainy pixels not aligned with the four primary features. Rainy pixels within a specific feature boundary are considered associated with that feature object. For frontal systems represented as line segments, the line-segment masks are expanded outward by 250 km to generate two-dimensional bounded features. The identification of precipitation sources is conducted independently every 6 hours over 19 years (2001-2019).

Figure 1. The framework of data processing for GPM-IMERG feature-precipitation identifiers

Atmospheric features and corresponding algorithms

Details of algorithms implemented for feature detection are described below:

- Atmospheric River:** Toolkit for Extreme Climate Analysis Bayesian AR Detector (TECA-BARD; O'Brien, et al., 2020) was implemented to identify binary masks of ARs determined by the integrated vapor transport (IVT) field which integrates the total amount of water vapor transport in the atmospheric column. The algorithm uses threshold values of IVT, areal extent, and a latitude filter to avoid tracking the

inter-tropical convergence zone (ITCZ). In addition, TECA-BARD includes a set of “plausible” AR detectors sampled by a Bayesian framework trained by experts’ judgments, which systematically replicates how experts determine ARs. Under the Bayesian framework, TECA-BARD provides a more strict criterion for global AR detection than a simple IVT-dependent detection.

- **Frontal system:** Global frontal systems are detected using an objective front identification algorithm (Sansom and Catto, 2022). A front is identified by line segments showing sharp horizontal gradients in the wet-bulb potential temperature field (θ_w) at 850 hPa (i.e., the baroclinic zone), suggesting a substantial difference in the thermodynamic properties of the air mass separated by the front. The identified front is then assigned to one of three front types based on the horizontal wind vector at 850 hPa with the direction pointing from the high to the low sector of θ_w , which includes cold ($< -1.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), warm ($> 1.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), and quasi-stationary fronts (in any front speed between -1.5 and 1.5 m s^{-1}).
- **Mesoscale convective system:** The FLEXible object TRackKeR (FLEXTRKR) is a flexible atmospheric feature tracking software package, which provides specific capabilities to track convective clouds including both individual convective cells and mesoscale convective systems using radar, satellite, and model data (Feng et al., 2021; Feng et al., 2023). In this study, cloud tracking is performed with hourly brightness temperature-defined cold cloud shields (CCSs, which include cold cloud cores and cold anvils) and precipitation features to improve the identification of robust MCSs. CCSs are first identified as contiguous regions of pixels with brightness temperatures $< 241 \text{ K}$, and with a distinct cold core (temperature $< 225 \text{ K}$). An MCS is then defined as a tracked CCS with (1) CCS $> 4 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$ containing a precipitation feature (connected raining pixels of 3 mm hr^{-1}) with a major axis length $> 100 \text{ km}$, (2) precipitation feature area, mean rain rate, rain rate skewness, and heavy rain volume ratio larger than the corresponding lifetime-dependent thresholds, and (3) both point (1) and (2) lasting continuously for longer than 4 hours. Using both CCS and PF to track MCS reduces the chance of identifying a cloud deck without the accompanying deep convection that produces heavy precipitation as an MCS.
- **Low-pressure system:** An automated Lagrangian pointwise feature tracker, TempestExtremes (Ullrich & Zarzycki, 2017) is utilized for low-pressure system (LPS) detection. Tropical-subtropical LPSs (35°S - 35°N) are tracked based on the stream function at 850 hPa (Vishnu et al. 2020). The detection requires the maximum surface geopotential within a 2° latitude/longitude range around the LPS center to be less than $8,000 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ for at least 24 cumulative hours of this LPS track. LPSs that spend nearly their entire lifetime over elevated terrain are excluded from the dataset. In addition, we only extract “moist” LPSs where relative humidity at 850 hPa exceeds 85% for a cumulative period of at least one day to avoid overly sampling including heat-induced

LPSs (e.g., Saharan heat lows) that are not relevant for precipitation. Tropical cyclones are implicitly embedded as a subset of the LPS data. A 10-degree square box is determined to represent the bounded area of an LPS in the current dataset.

3. Examples of data usage

Figure 2. An example of GPM-IMERG precipitation rate and identified atmospheric features: atmospheric river (AR), frontal system (front), mesoscale convective system (MCS), and low-pressure system (LPS) at 00Z on January 1st, 2017. The shading colors indicate the feature masks implemented to assign the 2-D map of precipitation identifiers.

Figure 3. A snapshot of GPM-IMERG V6 precipitation rate (Left) and the data product showing the classified PFIDs of rainy pixels (right) at 00Z on January 1st, 2017. The yellow contour overlaying the color shading in the left panel indicates the precipitation rate of 0.5 mm hr^{-1} . Hatched patterns indicate the double-feature (dot) and the triple-feature co-occurrence (slash), respectively. The acronyms of PFIDs in the legend are named by ordering individual components of the co-occurring features. For example, “AF” represents the co-occurrence of atmospheric rivers and fronts (AR-FT), and “AFM” for that of atmospheric rivers, fronts, and mesoscale convective systems (AR-FT-MCS).

Data source

GPM-IMERG precipitation V06 final version

(https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/datasets/GPM_3IMERGHH_06/summary?keywords=GPM%20IMERG%20Final%20Precipitation%20L3%20Half%20Hourly%20v6)

CPC MERGE-IR brightness temperature

(https://www.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/products/global_precip/html/wpage.merged_IR.html)

Data of identified atmospheric features: the collection of datasets is archived at NERSC High Performance Storage System (HPSS) (global/cfs/cdirs/m4374/catalogues/raw_catalogue_files/observations/)

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